

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN KENYA. CASE OF GARISSA LEVEL FIVE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the influence of conflict management as a strategy on performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya while locking the knowledge gap. The specifically, the research was to; establish the relationship between conflict strategies; avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies dominating strategies as well as compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya. The underpinning theories included the Thomas Kilmann theory, the Human Relations theory, and the Expectancy theory. The study used mixed approach (quantitative and qualitative approaches) and employed the pragmatism philosophy while adopting descriptive research design. It used the 297 health workers of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya as its target population. Using Yamane's formula, a sample of 168 participants was obtained and the participants was chosen using purposeful proportional random sampling. Data for this research were gathered from primary sources that used a questionnaire administered through a drop and pick method. The data was analyzed quantitatively for descriptive s and inferential statistics (correlation and multiple regression. The study found that each of avoidance strategies ($r = 0.582$; $\beta = 0.193$; $p = 0.021$), accommodating techniques ($r = 0.586$; $\beta = 0.093$; $p = 0.024$), dominating strategies ($r = 0.421$, $\beta = 0.167$; $p = 0.035$), and compromising strategies ($r = 0.491$; $\beta = 0.065$; $p < 0.01$) had a moderately significant effect on the performance of Garissa level five hospital. The study recommends that the public hospitals in Kenya should; strengthen their conflict management policy to indicate usage ant of; avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies as well as compromising strategies.

Keywords: Accommodating Strategies, Avoidance Strategies, Compromising, Conflict Management Strategies, Dominating Strategies, Performance of Public Hospital

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Globally, unexpected and pre-planned conflicts, brought on by disparities in religion, culture, ideologies, political power, cultural, social, and status interests, are persistently occurring among warring parties and even in different nations, (Einarsen et al., 2018). This explains why organizations continue to devise new approaches to avoid and solve conflicts in order to improve employee and organizational performance. Moreover, according to Way, Jimmieson and Bordia (2019), the inability for managements to manage conflicts at the work place effectively and establish positive resolutions cost companies cross the globe approximately

one full day of productivity every month. Conflict management can be described as the ability of organizations to identify the sources of conflicts and as well devise strategic measures to control, prevent, or minimize disputes or conflicts (Grubaugh & Flynn, 2018). Organizations rely on different models of conflict management to identify, assess, and implement the most appropriate actions or strategies when conflicts arise at the workplace. Blake and Mouton model, Thomas Kilman model, and Holton model are only a few examples (Sumitha & Rowena, 2016).

Conflict management strategies are futuristic, comprehensive approaches aimed at securing long-term gains for disputing parties. Negotiation (or collective bargaining), mediation or third-party interventions, leadership, brainstorming, and communication are some of these techniques (Olson et al., 2019). Importantly, conflict management approaches are based on the idea that while disputes cannot always be resolved, they may be managed via appropriate activities such as collaboration, accommodation, compromise, avoidance, and confrontation (Perez et al, 2016). According to Sammy (2016), there was a link between conflict management strategies and employee productivity, and the most popular strategies were integrating, avoiding strategy, obliging strategy, and integrating strategy.

According to Francis (2019), conflict is considered as inevitable and is currently a problem in virtually all public hospitals. Public hospitals have recently been viewed as a source of conflict in the country. They are an expression of communal disputes on several occasions. Managers and administrators must be able to spot conflict and treat it as a priority. As a result, Kenyan health sector management should ensure that there are clear conflict resolution procedures that control their staff, as well as a defined strategy to resolving disagreements. It is for this reason this study was conducted on the Kenyan public health sector and with specific interest in Garissa County

1.2 Statement of the problem

Kenyan healthcare systems function well in most counties. However, Garissa County is still struggling to stabilize its health function (Moses et al., 2020). More specifically, Garissa Level 5 hospital has reportedly been registering declining performance, which is associated with inadequate conflict management strategies. Accordingly, the hospital has been registering conflict on the way the management perceives remunerations, promotions as well transfers and redeployment and the way the other health staff perceive it (Ministry of State for Development of Northern Kenya and other Arid Lands [MONDKAL], 2018). Due to inadequate conflict management strategies, there has been prolonged conflicts that have resulted in a series of strikes and discontent among health employees, resulting in worsening performance at the Garissa Level 5 Hospital. Subsequently, Garissa Level 5 Hospital is facing problems ensuring quality and equitable access to health care for residents of Garissa, which is adversely affecting their health status (Pandey, 2018). So, Garissa Level 5 Hospital needs a well-functioning public healthcare system to continuing making headway toward ensuring decent health care for all residents of the county (Barasa, Nguhiu & McIntyre, 2019).

While Pandey (2018) confides that literature on strategy for promoting Kenyan health sector is limited, Abdi (2017) posits that there is a limitation of published empirical research on the factors that influence performance in the health sector in Kenya. That is, it is yet to be made clear the relation between conflict management and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya. With a view to improving the performance of Garissa Level 5 hospital, there was a need for more research to authenticate conflict management as a strategy for enhancing performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya, hence this study to fill the gap.

1.3 Objectives

The objective of the study was to establish the relationship between conflict management strategies and performance of public hospitals in Kenya and specifically:

1. To establish the relationship between conflict avoidance strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya
2. To establish the relationship between conflict accommodating strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya
3. To establish the relationship between conflict dominating strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya
4. To establish the relationship between conflict compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

1.4 Research Hypothesis

Based on the objectives above, the research tested the following null hypotheses;

H₀₁: Conflict avoidance strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H₀₂: Conflict accommodating strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H₀₃: Conflict dominating strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H₀₄: Conflict compromising strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

In this investigation, Thomas Kilmann theory was used in order to identify variables influencing conflict management techniques at Garissa level 5 hospitals. Essentially, this theory, introduced by Thomas and Kilmann in 1976, is intended to grasp the various behaviors of certain individuals in a conflict situation (Tjosvold et al., 2014). Ideally, it focuses on two distinct viewpoints: assertiveness, which includes meeting individual demands, and cooperativeness, which is working together with others. The model examines the five primary conflict resolution techniques of integrating, dominating, accommodating, compromising, and avoiding, as well as the two opposing viewpoints of high assertive low high cooperative. Whenever these viewpoints are combined, a method of dispute settlement emerges. Dominating strategies, according to Thomas and Kilmann (1976) are assertive and uncommunicative, while accommodating strategies are unassertive and cooperative, as avoiding strategies are unwilling to cooperate and unassertive, while compromising strategies are partially proactive and partially cooperative, and integrating strategies are assertive and cooperative.

2.2 Empirical Review

Francis (2018) investigated the impact of the avoidance approach on staff performance in public health facilities, and found that the participants favored and agreed on the style. According to the research by Sammy (2016), employees who stay away from conflicts have a lower probability of having their performance negatively impacted. It was also highlighted that reducing disputes by making it easier for employees to agree reduces the length of time it takes to resolve a problem. Employees obeying their superiors was an effective approach to reduce conflict while harmonious coexistence among employees resulted in better performance.

Accommodating strategy, according to Khan, Langove, Shah, and Umair (2015), entails satisfying the other person, which leads to a high degree of concern for others. The strategy tends to preserve the interests of other parties while also providing for a new perspective on

the problem. M'mbwanga, Maore, and Were (2021) found a significant inverse association between accommodating attitude and performance among MFIs in Nairobi while Francis (2018) showed that participants favored it. Sammy (2016) revealed that when workers raise grievances, they are rarely fully resolved and have a high probability of recurring in the future.

The dominant strategies is based on the utilization of an individual's position power (Tetteh & Obuobisa-darko, 2016). According to M'mbwanga, et al. (2021), there is a strong positive association between dominant approach and Microfinance institution performance. According to the research by Sammy (2016), managing employees with a dominating technique causes fear and makes employees afraid to speak up, resulting in just the superior party, the management, emerging as the victor, and therefore only a few employees supported controlling. The study also revealed that using force to resolve conflicts is ineffective.

Dominating can be employed as a fallback alternative (Khalid & Fatima, 2016). M'mbwanga et al. (2021) identified a substantial inverse relationship between compromise strategy and MFI performance. Kagwiria (2019) found that compromise has a positive and significant influence on organizational success. The finding in the research by Abazeed (2017) show that compromise has a significant impact on organizational commitment, while Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016) study result show a link between employee happiness and their readiness to compromise. According to Nzuve & Mwangi (2015), when employees in a firm perform well, it is mostly due to the direction and mentorship provided by the managers who oversee them.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.2 Research design

The current study adopted a descriptive research approach to gather data on conflict management tactics and their impact on the productivity of Kenya's healthcare system. Descriptive research design was chosen owing to its effectiveness in defining the factors of interest and its ability to provide in-depth insights into the study issue; which was demanded for in the present research. It was employed in the definition, estimation, forecasting, and analysis of synergistic associations (Creswell & Creswell, 2017)..

3.5 Target Population

The target population of the study was the 297 health officers of Garissa Level 5 Hospital (KEHPCA, 2020). The main reason for choosing this population was that they faced or experienced conflicts at the workplace, and know how the organization has been handling conflicts at the workplace and how that impacts the organization's performance.

3.3 Sampling

The study's sample size was determined using the methodology proposed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Krejcie and Morgan (1970) employ small sample approaches to determine sample size, employing the formula stated as

$$n = \frac{x^2NP(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (x^2P(1-P))}$$

Where n is the sample size,

x^2 Is chi-squared =3.81

N is the target population size

P = the population proportion (assumed to be .50) since this would provide the maximum sample size).

d = the degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion (.05)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus } n &= \frac{3.81 \times 297 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{[0.05 \times 0.05(297-1)] + 3.81 \times 0.5(1-0.5)} \\ &= \frac{3.81 \times 297 \times 0.25}{[0.0025 \times 296] + 3.81 \times 0.25} = \frac{282.89}{0.74 + 0.95} = \frac{282.89}{1.69} = 167.45 = 168 \end{aligned}$$

As a result, the sample size for the study was 168 respondents.

The size of the sample per categorization was determined using proportional sampling. Using sample frames, the study employed the systematic sampling approach to choose participants from each categorization of health workers.

3.4 Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data for this investigation (Kothari, 2012). The data was collected using a 5-point Likert scale. The likert scale is a set of scales that can be used to convert qualitative answers into numerical values (Gupta & Rangi, 2014). While collecting primary data, the questionnaire was administered using a drop-and-pick method (Creswell, 2014). The researchers employed an online questionnaire method to conduct the surveys when respondents were working outside of the office. The researcher created an online questionnaire, using goggle form, which was shared on the respondents' emails.

3.5 Data analysis and presentation

The Quantitative data was analysed using quantitative analysis to provide descriptive statistics (Creswell, 2014). Descriptive statistics were used to better comprehend and assess the study's outcomes, as well as to identify patterns, tendencies, and connections. Figures, tables, and narratives were used to convey information. Frequencies and percentages were utilized to examine data trends in the descriptive statistics study.

Inferential analysis was also performed utilizing both correlational analysis and multiple regressions analysis to get inferential statistics (correlational and inferential) at probability value (p-value); $\alpha = 0.05$). The correlation, which used Pearson's Product Moment, was to establish existence of relationship between independent variables (IVs); avoidance, dominating, compromising, integrating and collaborating and the dependent variable (DV); performance of public hospitals in Kenya. Each of the IV was correlated to the DV using Pearson's product method (PPM) at 5% significance level.

Multiple regression will be used to establish a model which predicts performance of public hospitals in Kenya in terms of avoidance, dominating, compromising, integrating and collaborating. All IVs were regressed against the DV jointly using the equation;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where:

- Y = Performance of public hospital in Kenya
- β_0 is the constant term (intercept).
- $\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$ are the coefficients of the IVs; coefficients of avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies respectively
- X_1 = Avoidance strategies
- X_2 = Accommodating strategies
- X_3 = Dominating strategies
- X_4 = compromising strategies
- e = error term

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Response Rate

In this thesis, the research, out of the 168 168 respondents, 119 responded submitted back their filled responses. Thus, the response rate in the study data collection was 119(70.83%)

where, a majority of 81.51% of respondents were aged between 18 and 35 years while 12(10.08%) were on the ages between 36 to 45 years and 10(8.40%) were aged between 46 to 55 years. A majority of 85(71.43%) of the respondents had college diplomas in health disciplines while 23(19.33%) were university undergraduates and 11(9.24%) had post graduates degree holders

4.2 Descriptive Analysis of Study Variables

The research objectives influenced the analysis, where the quantitative study generated descriptive statistics, that were used to characterize the features of the studied variables and, more crucially, portray the relationship between the independent variables (IVs) and the dependent variable (DV). The research implemented methods to interpret the findings in this regard.

4.4.1 Performance of Garissa level five hospital

The results obtained for performance of Garissa level five hospital were recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: performance of Garissa level five hospital

Performance indicators	M	SD
We effectively attend to patients visiting our facility	2.89	1.27
The employees are always motivated to delivery of their service effectively	2.85	1.19
The patients are always satisfied with employee service delivery	3.10	1.23
We have been registering high levels of employee productivity	2.58	1.17
Employees in our entity possess a high sense of belongingness	3.33	1.23
There is high productivity at our hospital	3.02	1.24
Performance of Garissa level five hospital	2.96	1.22

Source: Field data (2022)

Grounded on the results in Table 1, performance of Garissa level five hospital was indicated has having been moderate (M= 2.96, SD = 1.22). Specifically, the participants were not certain whether they effectively attended to patients visiting in the facility or not (M= 2.89, SD = 1.27) as they were also not sure whether the employees were always motivated to delivery of their service effectively (M= 2.85, SD = 1.19). While they showed neutrality on the assertion that the patients were always satisfied with employee service delivery (M= 3.10, SD = 1.23), they were showed that they had not been registering high levels of employee productivity (M= 2.58, SD = 1.17). More findings portray the respondents as showing neutrality on the assertion that employees in their entity possessed a high sense of belongingness (M= 3.33, SD = 1.23) indicated they were not sure whether there was high productivity at the hospital or not (M= 3.02, SD = 1.24).

These findings justify those in the study Moses et al. (2020) that Garissa County is still struggling to stabilize its health function was registering declining performance. These findings agree with Abdi (2017) that there are problems of employee dissatisfaction at Garissa level five hospital. According to MONDKAL (2018), Garissa level five hospital there is conflict on the way the management perceives things and the way health staff perceive it, which has led to low staff motivation and satisfaction.

4.4.2 Avoidance strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

The study assessed the first objective; establish the relationship between avoidance strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya to produce results in Table 2.

Table 2: Effects of avoidance strategies on the performance

Avoidance strategies	M	SD
We always avoid confrontation about their differences when discussing conflict matters	2.39	1.26
As much as possible we always avoid differences of opinion	2.22	1.21
We always seek to make any looming differences to be less severe	2.22	1.25
We always try to avoid any confrontation among conflicting sides	2.16	1.27
We always negotiate such that compromise can be reached easily	3.42	1.26
Effect of avoidance strategies	2.48	1.25

Source: Field data (2022)

In Table 2, it is shown that the respondents disagreed with assertion that they always avoided confrontation about their differences when discussing conflict matters (M= 2.39, SD = 1.26) as they disagreed with sentiment that as much as possible, they always avoided differences of opinion (M= 2.22, SD = 1.21). Moreover, they disagreed that they always sought o make any looming differences to be less severe (M= 2.22, SD = 1.25) and they further disagreed with the claim that they always tried to avoid any confrontation among conflicting sides (M= 2.16, SD = 1.27). Nevertheless, it was agreed that they always negotiate such that compromise could be reached easily (M= 3.42, SD = 1.26). The results show that the avoidance strategies had low impact on performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya (M= 2.48, SD = 1.25).

These findings confirm the findings in the research by Sammy (2016) that staying away from conflicts have a lower probability of having their performance negatively impacted. It was also highlighted that reducing disputes by making it easier for employees to agree reduces the length of time it takes to resolve a problem. Thus, harmonious coexistence among employees resulted in better performance. However, at Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya avoidance strategies were poorly employed to drive performance while at the same time the performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya was moderate. This is to mean that failure to fully employ avoidance strategies is related to the “strangling” performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya. The avoidance of confrontation about their differences when discussing conflict matters was low and as well as the hospital had poor strategies of avoiding differences of opinion. While the conflict management strategies function lowly made any looming differences to be less severe, there was low avoidance any confrontation among conflicting sides. However, they highly negotiated to ensure that compromise could be reached easily.

4.4.3 Accommodating strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

The study assessed the second objective; to establish the relationship between accommodating strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya to yield results captured in Table 3.

Table 3: Accommodating strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

Accommodating strategies	M	SD
Our conflict management meetings are always assertive and cooperative	3.44	1.26
We also seeking to improving relationships among conflicting parties	3.56	1.30
Our conflict management sessions seek for permanent and satisfactory solutions	2.81	1.24
At the end of the conflict management session all the parties are committed to the agreed upon resolutions	3.26	1.14
we examine issues until we find a solution that really satisfies him/her and the other party	3.27	1.13
We always stand for the goal and interests each party	3.42	1.20

We always examine ideas from both sides to find a mutually optimal solution	3.38	1.10
We work out a solution that serves interest of each party as much as possible	3.45	1.18
Effect of accommodating strategies	3.32	1.19

Source: Field data (2022)

The results in Table 3 show the respondent agreeing to the assertion that their conflict management meetings were always assertive and cooperative (M= 3.44, SD = 1.26). This was when it was agreed that they were also seeking to improving relationships among conflicting parties (M= 3.56, SD = 1.30). The argument that their conflict management sessions sought durable and satisfying solutions was met with neutrality (M= 2.81, SD = 1.24) and also showed neutrality on the claim that at the end of the conflict management session all the parties were committed to the agreed upon resolutions (M= 3.26, SD = 1.14). as they were not sure whether they looked into concerns until they discovered a solution that satisfied all parties (M= 3.27, SD = 1.13), they agreed that they always stood for the goal and interests each party (M= 3.42, SD = 1.20). Even though the responses always consider both sides' suggestions in order to achieve a mutually ideal outcome (M= 3.38, SD = 1.10), they agreed that they worked out a solution that serves interest of each party as much as possible (M= 3.45, SD = 1.18). Based on the results there was moderate employment of accommodating strategies (M= 3.32, SD = 1.19). Informed by these results, the employment of accommodating strategies in conflict management moderately affected the performance of Garissa level five hospital (M'mbwanga et al., 2021; Francis, 2018; Sammy, 2016). Francis (2018) research findings indicated that the expectations of the other parties engaged in the dispute are taken into account in accommodating strategies and that the approach protects human relationships and promotes organizational harmony. Accordingly, the accommodating style has a strong link to employee performance. This means that using moderate employment of accommodating strategies in conflict management would lead to moderate performance of Garissa level five hospital This accommodating strategy, according to Khan et al. (2015), entails pleasing the other person, which leads to a high level of concern for others. As proven in the current study, the strategy tends to protect the interests of the other stakeholders, allowing for a fresh look at the overall issue.

4.4.4 Dominating strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

The study assessed the third objective; to establish the relationship between dominating strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya to capture results in Table 4.

Table 4: Dominating strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

Dominating strategies	M	SD
In our meeting each party always only pushes its own point of view	2.67	1.13
Each party is always searching for its own gains	3.27	1.32
In our conflict management meeting each party fights for a good outcome for itself	3.30	1.21
Each does everything it can to win	3.47	1.29
We always make speedy decisions	3.36	1.14
There is exceedingly highly uncooperative conflict management meeting	3.21	1.37
Effect of dominating strategies	3.21	1.24

Source: Field data (2022)

Among these table 4 results, there was neutrality on the claim each party always only pushed its own point of view (M= 2.67, SD = 1.13) and that each party was always searching for its own gains (M= 3.27, SD = 1.32). Although they were neutral on the assertion that in their conflict management meeting each party fought for a good outcome for itself (M= 3.30, SD = 1.21), they agreed that each did everything it could to win (M= 3.47, SD = 1.29). They were

not sure whether they always made speedy decisions or not ($M= 3.36, SD = 1.14$) and were also not sure whether there were exceedingly highly uncooperative conflict management meetings ($M= 3.21, SD = 1.37$). Based on these results, the dominating strategies was moderately employed in conflict management ($M= 3.21, SD = 1.24$). Grounded on these results, there was moderate employment of dominating strategies in conflict management at Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya. However, M'mbwanga et al. (2021) reveal that dominating strategies and performance have a strong positive relationship. Thus, there is a significant and positive relationship between performance and dominating strategies. This is to mean that the moderate of performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya was associated to moderate employment of dominating strategies in conflict management at Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya. Sammy (2016) also revealed that using force to resolve conflicts is ineffective. Although a small percentage of workers felt that employee exploitation through low salaries aided in increasing performance, a large number of employees agreed that prompt decision making aided in enhancing employee performance. More so, Francis (2018) showed that the approach is widely utilized in public health facilities and is one of the most widely used conflict resolution strategies.

4.4.5 Compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

The study assessed the fourth objective; to establish the relationship between compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya; producing Table 5.

Table 5: Compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital

Compromising strategies	M	SD
We always try to realize a middle ground when seeking for solutions	2.73	1.15
Our managers are always seeking for temporal solutions	3.45	1.20
our meeting resolutions are always partially assertive	3.39	1.05
We strive to realise a cooperative resolution to conflict	3.53	1.25
Our facility always emphasizes on having to find a compromise solution	3.41	1.21
When seeking to resolution our management always insist either giving a little	3.35	1.19
Whenever possible we always strive towards a fifty-fifty compromise	3.38	1.17
Effect of compromising strategies	3.32	1.17

Source: Field data (2022)

Table 5 show that although the respondents showed neutrality on the assertion that they always tired try to realize a middle ground when seeking for solution ($M= 2.73, SD = 1.15$), they agreed that their managers were always seeking for temporal solutions ($M= 3.45, SD = 1.20$). While the respondents were neutral on the assertion that their meeting resolutions were always partially assertive ($M= 3.39, SD = 1.05$), they agreed that they strived to realize a cooperative resolution to conflict ($M= 3.53, SD = 1.25$) and agreed that their facility always emphasized on having to find a compromise solution ($M= 3.41, SD = 1.21$). While neutrality was prevalent on assertion that when seeking to resolution our management always insisted either giving a little ($M = 3.35, SD = 1.19$), claim that whenever possible they always endeavored towards a fifty-fifty compromise was associated with neutrality ($M= 3.38, SD = 1.17$). These findings show that compromising strategies was moderately employed in conflict management ($M= 3.32, SD = 1.17$). Founded on these results, compromising strategies was moderately employed in conflict management. Meanwhile, the research by Kagwiria (2019) found that compromising strategies has a positively significant impact on performance. Compromise approach may provide a temporary solution while still looking for a win-win situation, and compromise emphasizes something that is frequently overlooked in personal and commercial interactions. Based on the findings by Kagwiria (2019), then the

moderate performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya may be attributed to the moderate employment of compromising strategies in conflict management. But this study found that managers were always seeking for temporal solutions they strived to realize a cooperative resolution to conflict while the conflict management meeting always emphasized on having to find a compromise solution. On the other hand, Abazeed (2017) found that compromise has a major impact on organizational commitment in his study. More so, Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016) found that there is a significant relationship between employee satisfaction and willingness to compromise. This implies that conflict resolution approaches such as compromise aid in improving performance (Gitonga, 2015).

4.5 Inferential Analysis

4.5.1 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was performed using Pearson's product method (PPM) at a 5% (0.05) level of significance to determine the presence of a link between the DV and each IVs; avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies and the results presented in table 6.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis statistics

		Performance	Avoidance strategies	Accommodating strategies	Dominating strategies	Compromising strategies
Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.582**	.586**	.421**	.491**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	119	119	118	117	116
Avoidance strategies	Pearson Correlation	.582**	1	.607**	.415**	.412**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	119	119	118	117	116
Accommodating strategies	Pearson Correlation	.586**	.607**	1	.423**	.377**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
	N	118	118	118	117	116
Dominating strategies	Pearson Correlation	.421**	.415**	.423**	1	.321**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00
	N	117	117	117	117	115
Compromising strategies	Pearson Correlation	.491**	.412**	.377**	.321**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	N	116	116	116	115	116

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field data (2022)

In here, each of the IV; avoidance strategies (p <0.001), accommodating strategies (p <0.001), dominating strategies (p<0.001), and compromising strategies (p <0.001), was significantly related to performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya since the p-value for each was less than 0.05. It is also demonstrated that avoidance strategies (p 0.001; r = 0.582), accommodating strategies (p 0.001; r = 0.586), dominating strategies (p 0.001; r = 0.421), and compromising strategies (p 0.001; r = 0.491) had a moderately significant relationship with the performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya, with the correlation coefficient (r) between 0.3 and 0.6 among these relationships, accommodating strategies (r = 0.586) had the highest then avoidance strategies (r = 0.582) which was followed by compromising strategies (r = 0.491) and lastly dominating strategies (r = 0.421).

4.5.3 Regression Analysis

Table7: Regression Results

	Coefficients				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.383	.431		.889	.376
Avoidance strategies	.193	.082	.193	2.337	.021

Accommodating strategies	.213	.093	.188	2.281	.024
Dominating strategies	.130	.061	.167	2.135	.035
Compromising strategies	.302	.065	.375	4.668	.000

a. Dependent Variable: performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya

Source: Field data (2022)

The findings (T= 2.337; p= 0.021) were used to test the first hypotheses

H₀₁: Conflict avoidance strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H_{a1}: Conflict avoidance strategies significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

These outcomes demonstrate that at $\alpha= 0.05$, avoidance strategies have a significant effect on the performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya. So the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate accepted and henceforth there is substantial proof that avoidance strategies are a useful estimator of performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya.

According to the findings, the p-value <0.05; (T= 2.281; p = 0.024), for testing the hypotheses;

H₀₂: Conflict accommodating strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H_{a2}: Conflict accommodating strategies significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya.

there is a significant association between accommodating techniques and the performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya. There is extensive proof that accommodating techniques are useful estimators of performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya at the 0.05, 5% significance level.

From the outcomes, (T= 2.135; p= 0.035), produced on testing hypotheses;

H₀₃: Conflict dominating strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H_{a3}: Conflict dominating strategies significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya.

the p-value is less than 0.05 is a signal that there is a substantial association between dominating techniques and performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya. As a result, at 0.05, there is substantial proof that the prevailing strategy is a useful indicator of Garissa level five hospital's performance.

The hypotheses

H₀₄: Conflict compromising strategies do not significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya

H_{a4}: Conflict compromising strategies significantly affect performance of Garissa level five Hospital in Kenya.

Were tested based on the finding, the p-value is less than 0.05 (T= 4.666; p< 0.01). These results are indicating that there is a significant relationship between compromising strategies and performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya, and at 0.05, there is substantial proof that compromising strategies is a useful estimator of performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya.

So, avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies have a considerable impact on Garissa level five hospital's performance and are

thus appropriate estimators of Garissa level five hospital's performance. According to the findings, the most significant effect is compromise tactics (=0.302), followed by accommodating strategies (= 0.213), avoidance techniques (=0.193), and finally dominating strategies (= 0.130).

To get a linear regression equation, the model is derived using the results in Table 4.15.;

Performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya (\hat{Y}) = 0.383cons + 0.193 avoidance strategies (X_1) + 0.213 accommodating strategies (X_2) + 0.130 dominating strategies (X_3) + 0.302 compromising strategies (X_4)

Table 8: Model Summary

Model Summary			
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.560 ^a	.3137	.2896	.64205

a. Predictors: (Constant), compromising strategies, dominating strategies , accommodating strategies, avoidance strategies

Source: Field data (2022)

As per the results in table 4.16, the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.3137 indicates that avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies explain 31.37 percent of the change in performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya.

ANOVA statistics are used to determine whether the model is insignificant in estimating the performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya. Table 9 summarizes the findings.

Table 9: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Regression	21.481	4	5.370	13.027	.000 ^b	
Residual	46.993	114	.412			
Total	68.474	118				

a. Dependent Variable: performance of Garissa level five hospital, Kenya

b. Predictors: (Constant), compromising strategies, dominating strategies , accommodating strategies, avoidance strategies

Source: Field data (2022)

The results reveal that p-value = 0.000 in (F= 14.489, P<0.01), which is smaller than p-value 0.05. Since p-value 0.05, there is enough evidence to suggest that at least one of the avoidance tactics, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies is effective in explaining the performance of Garissa level five hospital in Kenya. According to the data, (F4,118 = 14.489) is more than (F-critical4,118 = 2.445), providing adequate evidence to determine that your model is significant. Because the F-test is significant, R-squared does not equal zero, indicating that the relationship between the model and the dependent variable is statistically significant.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

According to the findings, avoidance methods have a somewhat moderate significant influence on the functioning of Kenyan public hospitals. This is through; encompassing strategies that would emphasis on avoidance of confrontation about differences when discussing conflict matters, strategizing to ensure avoiding differences of opinion, providing for opportunity to make any looming differences to be less severe, having strategies that avoid any confrontation among conflicting sides, and developing approaches that advocate for highly negotiating all arising issues to ensure that compromise is easily reachable

According to the findings, accommodating methods have a moderately favorable significant influence on public hospital performance in Kenya. This strategy involves establishing an approach that provides forceful and cooperative conflict management meetings, improving relationships between opposing parties, encouraging all parties to adhere to all agreed-upon resolutions ensuring that all concerns are addressed until an amicable solution is found, studying concerns from both sides in order to discover a mutually optimal solution, as well as working out a solution that serves each party's interests.

The research concluded that dominant techniques have a moderately positive significant influence on public hospital performance in Kenya. The right tactics for improving public hospital performance in Kenya need; adding procedures that encourage each party to always press its own point of view, urging each party to fight for a favorable outcome that is focused on winning its case at some point, making quick judgments.

Finally, the study concludes that compromising methods have a moderately positive significant influence on public hospital performance in Kenya. Compromise tactics for improving public hospital performance in Kenya are designed to focus on achieving a middle ground while finding a solution, where the parties should strive for a fifty-fifty compromise. As a result, compromising techniques should focus finding a compromise solution in which each party is willing to give a little when seeking a resolution. If the disagreement is difficult to resolve quickly, there should be options for finding temporary solutions. Compromise tactics for meeting resolutions should always be partially assertive, with the goal of achieving a cooperative conflict settlement.

Finally, the study finds that at a 5% (0.05) level of significance, each of the following techniques had a substantial impact on public hospital performance in Kenya: avoidance strategies, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies. As a result, avoidance techniques, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies are all powerful predictors of public hospital performance in Kenya. While avoidance, domineering, and compromising methods are all directly proportional to the performance of public hospitals in Kenya, accommodating strategies are only indirectly proportional. According to the study, avoidance techniques, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies account for 31.37 percent of changes in public hospital performance in Kenya.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Recommendations on Research Findings

The study made policy recommendation guided by the study findings. Firstly, the study recommends that the public hospitals in Kenya should review their avoidance strategies and adopt those strategies in their human resources management strategies. They should importantly include provision in their conflict management polices to allay any confrontation about differences when discussing conflict matters and should ensure that there is guideline to ensure they guide during differences of opinion.

Secondly, the study recommends that public hospitals in Kenya should actively encourage employment of accommodating strategies in their conflict management guidelines. There should structure to ensure that all issues need to be examined until a solution that really satisfies all other parties and the goal and interests each party area addressed so as to find a mutually optimal solution which serves interest of each party.

Thirdly, the study recommends that during times of difficult situation (when the demands are unreasonable), public hospitals in Kenya should employ dominating strategies. This is where individual parties will be allowed to pushed their own point of view for their own gains and therefore fight for a good outcome for itself. In this case speedy decisions will be appropriate but there should be exceedingly highly cooperative conflict management meetings.

Lastly, the study recommends that public hospitals in Kenya should always employ compromising strategies in their conflict management and even review their policies where the team should always seek to realize a middle ground when seeking for solution. In this

case, meeting resolutions deserve to be partially assertive while sometimes endeavoring towards a fifty-fifty compromise and striving to realize a cooperative resolution to conflict.

5.2.2 Recommendations for Further Study

Based on the study findings and methodology, the present made some suggestions for further study which are

- i. The current study relies on data received from primary sources via a questionnaire. This information was totally subjective. As a result, a similar study using secondary data should be conducted to confirm the current study's conclusions.
- ii. The study discovered that avoidance techniques, accommodating strategies, dominating strategies, and compromising strategies account for 31.37 percent of the difference in public hospital performance in Kenya. This suggests that the remaining 69.63 percent is explained by other factors. As a result, the study suggests that more research be done to determine what factors affect the 69.63 percent improvement in public hospital performance in Kenya.

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